

What Role Does Media Representation Play In The Radicalisation And Public Perception Of Groups?

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Signing out, Tieah Richardson xx

Abstract

This dissertation investigates the role of media representation in the radicalisation process and its impact on public perception of extremist groups. This literature-based study uses media framing and cultivation theories to understand and potentially mitigate radicalisation. Through a literature review, it examines how media portrayals shape societal understanding of extremist groups across social media platforms. The method involves using existing research on media framing techniques, such as conflict, human interest, and consequence, and their effects on public opinion and stereotypes. Analysis of media coverage referring to counterterrorism and Islamophobia in the UK post-9/11 to illustrate how frames all influence public attitudes. The results highlight how long-term exposure to media can feed into the susceptibility of radicalisation as sensationalistic content becomes normalised. In conclusion, the results reveal the media's significant impact on shaping beliefs and social realities, without a doubt contributing to radicalisation. Research underscores the importance of understanding media's role in shaping public perceptions, offering insights for adopting more informed and critical media consumers.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Radicalisation has risen as a central concern within contemporary security discourse, shaping policy, radicalisation efforts and public perception across the United Kingdom and beyond. Ever since the 9/11 terrorist attacks birthing the “War on Terror” counter-terrorism efforts and the proliferation of extremist ideologies, governments and institutions have hardened efforts to understand and counter the processes which lead up to radical or violent beliefs and movements. The UK’s Counter-Terrorism Strategy, particularly through its PREVENT programme, has poised radicalisation not only as a security threat but as a social and ideological challenge that requires a multi-factorial response. Understanding the factors that contribute to radicalisation and how the public perceives groups associated with extremism is vital for crafting effective policies and interventions. One of the key factors believed to shape this process is media representation. The digital age, the continual rise of social media and 24-hour news cycles has transformed the way in which we survey media and its influence on radicalisation as well as public perception. Social media platforms, with their algorithmic synthesis and viral potential have become echo chambers where extremist ideologies can spread rapidly. The accessibility and anonymity these platforms behold make them attractive places for radical groups to disperse propaganda, recruit new members, and shape public discourse. Furthermore, the mainstream media plays a crucial role in framing the narrative around radicalisation, often influencing public attitudes and perceptions of certain groups. The power of media representation in shaping societal understanding of extremism is very much prevalent and is a growing, concerning issue.

1.2 Research Aim

This dissertation aims to explore the intricate relationship between media representation, radicalisation, and public perception, focusing particularly on how media portrayals shapes both the radicalisation process and the public’s understanding of extremist groups. The study will investigate how media framing and cultivation shape public opinion, stereotypes, and discrimination, particularly in relation to sensitive topics such as terrorism. The following research will look at the media’s role in shaping perceptions of extremist groups and also seeks to provide insights that can inform strategies to mitigate the negative impacts of media representation, learning more informed public discourse.

To achieve this aim, the dissertation will answer these key questions:

- How does media representation contribute to the radicalisation process, both directly through the dispersion of extremist ideologies and indirectly through shaping public attitudes and perceptions?
- What theoretical frameworks, such as Media Framing Theory and Cultivation Theory, best explain the impact of media representation on radicalisation and public perception?
- How do specific media framing techniques, such as conflict framing, human interest framing, and responsibility framing, influence public attitudes toward extremist groups?
- To what extent does media exposure cultivate distorted social realities and normalise ideologies, contributing to the radicalisation process?
- What are the implications of these findings for specialist such as media researchers and educators in terms of developing strategies to counter radicalisation and promote responsible media coverage.

To answer these questions, the chapter structure is as follows: Chapter 2 will provide an in-depth review of the relevant literature on media representation, radicalisation, and public perception, focusing on the theoretical frameworks of Media Framing Theory and Cultivation Theory. Chapter 3 will present a detailed analysis of media coverage of extremist groups in the UK, examining how different framing techniques are used to portray these groups and influence public attitudes. Chapter 4 will explore the role of social media in the radicalisation process, focusing on how extremist ideologies are dispersed and consumed on these platforms. Chapter 5 will delve into media's role as a recruitment tool for vulnerable individuals seeking identity, community, or purpose, focusing on how media narratives contribute to public polarisation. Finally, Chapter 6 will examine how media can generate "moral panic" and fact distortion, particularly through the "War on Terror" and reviewing studies on how media portrayals of radicalised groups deepen fear and prejudice.

1.3 Methodology

The aim of this literature review is to evaluate how media representation influences the radicalisation stages and what kind of people are susceptible to being exposed to the algorithm they come across online. Also focusing on the public perception of extremist groups, including terrorist organisations, political extremists, and other radicalised factions as mild as media cults on accessible social media platforms like the former Twitter (now X), TikTok, Instagram. The review will look at existing research

on the ways media portrayal shapes societal understanding of these groups and the pathways through which it may contribute to or mitigate radicalisation. The rise of extremist groups in the digital age, coupled with the growing influence of social media and 24-hour news cycles, makes the role of media in shaping both the radicalisation process and the public's perception of these groups a pressing issue.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Media Theories

This chapter will provide an in-depth rationale of Media Framing Theory and its impact on public perception, particularly in the context of media coverage of terrorism and societal issues. It will begin by introducing the foundational concepts of Media Framing Theory, including its origins in the work of Bateson (1972) and the contributions from Goffman (1974) and Entman (1991). The chapter will then differentiate Media Framing theory from Agenda Setting Theory, highlighting how both theories guide public discourse in distinct ways: Agenda Setting dictates what topics are discussed, while Media framing shapes how those topics are perceived and interpreted. The discussion will move on to a detailed examination of the primary framing techniques identified by Entman, such as Conflict, Human Interest, Consequence, Responsibility, and Humanisation, with a focus on how these techniques are used by the media to influence audience perceptions. Real-world applications of these framing techniques will be illustrated through the analysis of media coverage surrounding terrorism in the UK post-9/11, particularly the frames of Inevitability and Preparedness and Belonging and Responsibility, and their implications for public attitudes toward Muslim communities. The chapter will conclude by discussing the importance of understanding Media Framing Theory in the context of criminology and media studies. It will emphasize how the theory is applied to assess the influence of media on public opinion, stereotypes, and discrimination, particularly in relation to sensitive topics such as terrorism. The theoretical insights provided in this chapter will be positioned as critical tools for fostering more informed and critical media consumers. Within this chapter, the exploration of Cultivation Theory focuses on media theory that explains how long-term exposure to media, shapes how people see the world, more specifically the new qualifications of the theory including “Mean World Syndrome”, mainstreaming and resonance. These three factors are highly interesting when linking this theory to the question at hand as the bigger someone relates, holds a victim complex or perhaps has shared personal grievances with the shown media, the more likely people become radicalised. This ties down to the way media exposure can influence public perception of extremist groups which will be evaluated.

2.2 Media Framing Theory

The Media Framing theory describes psychological frames as a “spatial and temporary bounding of a set of interactive messages” (Bateson, 1972). Framing theory is based on how information is presented and how this differs the way in which an audience will interpret it. Quite often, these interpretations

can be subtle to the extent we do not realise it's happening all around us in newspapers and on social media, suddenly we see the world through a different lens. Framing theory differs from Agenda Setting Theory (McCombs, 1972) which ultimately provokes ideas of what to think about, topically, while Media Framing Theory goes further, influencing how we think about those topics and entices us into thinking about certain controversies and breeding opinion on a topic (Arowolo, 2017). The more vigilant society are to the 'Media Framing' system, the less trusting to new sources that arise with spontaneous news, we become, ultimately meaning people become sceptical, critical consumers of information. By showcasing certain angles, media outlets can evoke opinions and judgements on complex issues, guiding public perception. **Agenda Setting** and **Media Framing** share a common foundation as they both illustrate the media's power in shaping public discourse. However, there are key distinctions, while Agenda Setting Theory focuses on telling us *what* to think about, Media Framing focuses on how to think about it. For instance, media outlets might emphasise a political scandal by framing it as a moral failing and using personal responsibility to convey the story or as a consequence of systemic corruption which frames the story as an issue of institutional failure. This subtle difference in framing can shift public attitudes, even when the same event is covered.

2.3 Goffman (1974) and Entman (1991)

Goffman (1974) argues that primary frameworks are essentially the mental filters we use to make sense of the world which are separated into two different types: Natural frameworks and social frameworks (Goffman, 1974). Initially we may interpret something that's happened 'naturally' like a tree that has fallen down as a purely physical occurrence due to the wind, however a social framework would see the human effect of the occurrence being disruptively moved due to deforestation or the tree being chopped down- the same event but different interpretations (Mass Communication Theory, 2017). The process of framing is activated through contextualisation, this helps organisations capture the audience by producing news which is predefined and significantly influences how the audience perceives the information. Entman (1991) pointed out that framing can be significantly difficult to detect as it can be perceived as being completely natural, he also suggested a helpful strategy: to compare different framing techniques which are commonly used within media. He looked at different sources which downplay aspects of information or make them more salient which unveil the framing choices made to go into national news and manipulate the media, being one of the most influential theories in mass communication cases (D'Angelo & Kuypers, 2010). Entman outlined 5 common ways that news stories are framed, the first being 'Conflict' which usually is associated with political coverage and use it as a deterrent from relevant manifestos and political movements and instead the drama surrounding parties and between different politicians. 'Human Interest/Personalisation' uses human faces to latch

onto our morality and is mostly used within charities for homelessness, underprivileged children, water famine countries, however it can also potentially overshadow the bigger picture, and that the media is hiding the whole truth from us to sympathise with a false underdog. 'Consequence' framing highlights the potential outcomes or ramifications of an issue whilst responsibility looks to attribute blame or credit for a situation (Entman, 1991).

2.4 Application of Framing Theory in Media Coverage

The practical application of Media Framing Theory is especially evident when examining the British media's coverage of counterterrorism and Islamophobia in the UK, particularly between 2001 and 2011. A particularly high activity of two main frames which were used in the coverage of 9/11 alleged plots. The first one being 'Inevitability and Preparedness' frame, post-9/11 the whole world lived in fear which this type of framing thrived on and focused on the urgency of alleged plots, often using language that insinuated a crisis was nigh which urged people to be vigilant, internationally (Mythen & Walklate, 2006). Secondly, 'Belonging and Responsibility' this frame focuses on the alleged plots and how they were increasingly shown as belonging to the Muslim communities where they first happened, this became more noticeable after the London bombings incident in 2005, instead of looking at bigger societal issues or government policies, all the blame looked directly at Muslim communities which heightened discrimination and created stigmas (Mathews, 2015). Vox-pops interviews with volunteers took place on the streets to give a voice to the communities involved but covertly reinforced that perhaps these are the people responsible for stopping terrorism within their own groups whilst also treating Muslims as one with intense suspicion. Journalists often drew on the perspectives of local communities, including family and friends instead of arrested individuals, however, this could also be argued to reinforce negative representations of Muslim communities and Islam by associating them with terrorism (Fink & Schudson, 2014).

2.5 Cultivation Theory

Cultivation Theory is a branch of media theory that attempts to suggest long-term exposure to television and other forms of media, can shape viewers perception of reality, often becoming reflective of fictional messages advanced by television (Gerbner, 1969). The origin of Gerbner's theory was to test the effects of television on participants over a short-term period, noticing the dominating effects lied in the long-term, ecological setting as people encounter media repeatedly over the course of their everyday lives (Vinney, 2019). As people's perceptions are influenced by media exposure, their beliefs, values and attitudes about social realities become skewed. This is particularly relevant in areas such as violently aggravated and racial stereotypes creating a false ideology and cult-like behaviours within

society. The focus on television came from the assessment of it as a mass medium, Gerbner proposed that it restricts choice because, as a mass medium, television must appeal to large, diverse audiences (Gerbner, 1998). However, Gerbner's research differed to usual media researchers, who most believe media violence and aggressive behaviour have a positive correlation, he was more focused on the fear that people culminate from watching a great deal of television, believing that crime and victimisation were rampant. 'Mean World Syndrome' was a term coined after the fact this phenomenon was discovered, especially after research showed more absent television users were more trusting and showed less fear towards the world in comparison to heavy television viewers (Gerbner, 1980). With establishment, soon came refinement of the Cultivation Theory to explain influence of media by suggesting two ideas known as mainstreaming and resonance. Mainstreaming is the process of television viewers who would once share very different views develop a homogenous view of the world, a mainstream perspective is cultivated through frequent exposure to the same television messages. Resonance is particularly concerning, and it occurs when a media message is particularly significant or personable to the individual because it somehow coincides with a viewer's lived experience (Vinney, 2019). People who unfortunately categorise into marginalised groups can resonate with hate crimes targeted towards them, this is shown in the media which enhances the belief that the world is a mean and scary place. Unlike mainstreaming, resonance builds on the idea that with experiences closer to mass media messages, the effect on the individual is greater (Shrum & Bischak, 2001).

2.6 Extent of Application to Media Portrayal

Cultivation theory has been widely used to understand the impact media has towards synthesis of stereotypes and social norms, media portrayals of specifically ethnic minorities and gender roles can contribute to the cultivation of stigmatised ideologies. A recent study conducted by Pollock (2021), examined the relation between cultivation theory and the portrayal of race within crime media which results showed that heavier viewers of crime-related content were more likely to adopt unrealistic views in relation to racial stereotypes in crime (Pollock, 2021). Ultimately, these portrayals can shape public perceptions about gender roles, race and social class which influences societal expectations and behaviours. Debates have arisen in literature which critics suggest Cultivation theory is reductionist of the correlation between media and perception, assuming that media exposure is the only influence on people's beliefs and attitudes, it ignores individual differences such as education, lived experiences and environmental influences which contribute to shaping our view on the world (Potter, 2014). This criticism was reinforced by Tyler & Cook (1980; 1984) where they termed the 'impersonal impact hypothesis', this qualification of Cultivation theory suggested that not every individual judges a crime and interprets perceived media the same as each other, based on their own relations to crime. This

may be one's own risk of crime victimisation, their own experience with crime or the frequency of societal crime around them which all of these culminated overrides the influence of TV information to judge their personal risk. Shrum & Bischak (2001) showed in subsequent research that the impersonal impact hypothesis stands plausible as their study of testing the judgement of personal crime risk in an individual's own neighbourhood and TV viewing showed no correlation either. This considers the fact that not everyone is susceptible to perceiving extremist views from the media, internally, and that personal experiences play a role in the process of radicalisation. However, in the circumstances of this dissertation, the relevance of cultivation theory is specifically focused on how prolonged exposure to media representations of radical/ extremist groups can shape public perceptions, normalise extreme ideologies, and contribute to the radicalisation process by influencing individuals' beliefs over time

2.7 Cultivation Theory and the Influence of Societal Attitudes on Extremist Ideologies

Cultivation theory can help explain how societal attitudes and beliefs are influenced by media, particularly in normalising or sensationalising extremist ideologies (Gerbner, 1980). When individuals are repeatedly exposed to extreme or sensationalised portrayals of violence, extremism, or radicalisation in the media, they may begin to internalise these portrayals as normality, coining a phrase which is known as "free advertising" (Wolfowicz et al, 2022). Terrorists use this to attract new recruits alongside strengthening a group image to their current supporters, particularly if they feel marginalised within society as this fuels the appetite of a sense of belonging from a spokesperson who will voice these extremist views (Weimann, 2005). Over time this repeated exposure creates an international view where extremist beliefs may seem more acceptable (Ahmed & Matthes, 2016) or even necessary to some individuals. In the case of extremist ideologies, media portrayals of violence or radical views may be sensationalised for shock value, creating an exaggerated sense of threat or urgency. This can lead to desensitisation, where the audience becomes less shocked by extremist actions, and over time, may begin to accept these ideologies as legitimate or justified (Matusitz, 2012). On the other hand, the media can also normalise extremist views by presenting them in a way that seems reasonable or mainstream, especially when framed as responses to perceived societal or political issues. Cultivation theory suggests that long-term media exposure doesn't just shape how people view extreme events; it also influences the broader societal attitudes that allow these ideologies to thrive. By continuously presenting these ideologies in certain ways, media can effectively normalise or sensationalise them, shaping public perception and potentially legitimising extremist views within society. In conclusion, Cultivation theory underscores the power of media in moulding societal attitudes toward extremism,

potentially fostering a culture in which radical ideologies become more accepted or sensationalised over time.

This literature review has explored the powerful role of media in shaping public perception, particularly with the justification of Media Framing Theory and Cultivation Theory, which both provide valuable constructs for understanding how radicalisation and extremist ideologies are normalised over time. Media Framing Theory demonstrates how the way stories are structured and presented, through specific language and emphasis, can subtly guide public attitudes particularly in the context of terrorism and marginalised communities. As seen in the analysis of post-9/11 media coverage in the UK, the framing events often reinforce fear, suspicion, and stigma, particularly toward Muslim communities, which influences society perceptions of responsibility and belonging. Meanwhile, Cultivation Theory provides insight into how long-term exposure can gradually alter individuals' perceptions of reality. Concepts such as Mean World Syndrome, mainstreaming, and resonance help explain how repeated portrayals of violence, fear, or extremism can influence not just individuals' perceptions but also create what are known as "echo chambers". In the context of this dissertation, these portrayals can contribute to the radicalisation process by making extreme ideologies seem more normalised and sometimes necessary, especially among people who feel marginalised or share similar grievances with the content presented. Both of these theories highlight how media does not inform public opinion but leads it in favourable directions and shapes it, it can be suggested that media provokes at legitimising extremist views and shaping public attitudes towards the groups associated with them whether this is through immediate framing or long-term effects of cultivation. Media representation plays a central and complex role in influencing how society understands fears or sympathises with radical ideologies. Putting these theories in context of themes within media, traditional vs social media, will help uncover the processes that go into perception shaping.

Chapter 3: Types of Media and Their Influence on Radicalisation

3.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss the way in which media representations plays a detrimental role in shaping public perceptions which leads to influencing the radicalisation of extremist groups, by focusing on literature which highlights the way mainstream news outlets report on these groups, mainly through sensationalism, framing choices, and political discourse, can challenged or support societal divisions. This section primarily assesses how media coverage contributes towards the depiction of extremism whilst examining the role of political rhetoric in fuelling societal polarisation.

3.2 Traditional Media Representation

Sensationalism is often prioritised within mainstream news outlets by focusing on the brutality and gory aftermath of attacks rather than the methodical ideologies and causes which led to the incident. The shock value that terrorism creates in the news makes journalists seem obligated to cover more stories in this nature, in turn making their acts more accessible and visible for international audiences which idealises terrorists as the largest contributors towards global conflicts (Narcos 2016; Weimann, 2012). To better understand the factors that drive media towards terrorism, most studies have focused on comparing the statistics based on coverage value for different attacks. Research involving interviews with journalists (Abubakar, 2020) as well as content analysis, shows that news values play a crucial role in deciding which attacks make the headlines (Hase, 2021; Kearns et al., 2019; Sui et al., 2017). Similarly, it's not just the attacks that gain attention; the people behind them are often covered too (Hoffman et al, 2010), with media often focusing on the grievances of the perpetrators (Chermak & Gruenewald, 2006). Graphic and emotionally charged language are frequently used to increase audience engagement, one study found that this type of content increases viewership by 42% compared to other analytical pieces (Farwell, 2014).

This sensationalist approach can simultaneously amplify extremist narratives, as discussed within the literature review within chapter 2.7, the Cultivation Theory suggests that exposure to sensationalistic media heightens the chance of people creating oppressive views which slowly tuns into echo chambers. Groups like ISIS have previously exploited this tendency by staging advanced attacks designed to attract

media attention and this disproportionate focus elevates the perceived importance of certain groups while marginalising others, creating an imbalance in public understanding of global extremism. Language is extremely important particularly in how extremist groups are perceived, most commonly it is Islamist groups that are labelled as "terrorists," this disparity reinforces stereotypes that associate terrorism exclusively with Islam while downplaying the ideological roots of far-right extremism. A study investigated by Agustian et al. (2024) analysed the effect media narratives have on perceptions of Islamic identity and terrorism, their findings revealed contrasting media depictions of ISIS, linking it to the United States' (U.S.) actions and Islamic identity, whilst also highlighting Russia's effort to separate Islam from radicalism in media portrayals (Agustian et al., 2024) Additionally, Islamist groups are frequently portrayed as external threats to Western society, with 79% of articles framing them as foreign dangers rather than addressing their ideological appeal within local communities (Berger & Morgan, 2015). In contrast, far-right groups are contextualised as domestic issues in 61% of cases, which can normalise their occurrence and reduce perceived urgency, ultimately this framing contributes to societal polarisation by reinforcing an us-versus-them narrative that alienates minority communities and fuels xenophobia (Coster et al., 2024; Vasist et al., 2023). These dynamics create feedback loops where media coverage both reflects and amplifies societal prejudices.

Political discourse often intersects with media representation to further exacerbate societal division which politicians frequently use inflammatory language that legitimises extremist narratives or reinforces societal othering. For instance, declarations like the "War on Terror" have increased media attention toward Islamist extremist groups, this was supported in a computational analysis of the U.S. and in the UK which found that ISIS received 64-80% of terrorism-related coverage between 2014 and 2016, without a single mention of comparable violence enforced by others like Boko Haram (Hellmeuller et al., 2021). This solidifies the idea that politicised discourse amplifies visibility for certain marginalised groups. Civilisational media has been blamed for framing conflicts as a clash of values which correlates with spikes in hate crimes against minority communities. The UK media in the aftermath of Brexit fuelled anti-Muslim hate crimes, rising by 19% for instance headlines tried to emphasise asylum seeker enforcement failures by publishing "12,000 are wanted", illustrating how persuasive media can translate into worldwide consequences (Ekstrom, 2022; Baker et al., 2012).

3.3 Social Media and Digital Platforms

This paragraph will discuss the topic social media and digital platforms, most importantly, their role they play in the radicalisation process and the public perception of extremist groups. These platforms have transformed how extremist ideologies are disseminated, amplified, and normalised, often

leveraging algorithms and user behaviour to create echo chambers that reinforce radical beliefs. This section explores the dynamics of social media in spreading extremist content, focusing on its impact on radicalisation and public perception, supported by case studies of groups like ISIS. Social media has made everything so much more accessible for the good and unfortunately for the bad, it is used as a powerful tool for extremist groups: as a place of recruitment, radicalisation and a way of transportation of individuals internationally.

For instance, ISIS has demonstrated decent proficiency in utilising platforms like Twitter to disseminate propaganda, promote religious ideology, and connect directly with potential recruits, with a study detecting 23.4% of extremists using the website between 2005-2016 (Safer-Lichtenstein et al., 2018). Meanwhile, in 2014 Berger & Morgan (2015) conducted a simultaneous study to find ISIS was operating approximately 46,000 Twitter accounts worldwide, relying on hyperactive users to push hashtags and messages to trending charts (Berger & Morgan, 2015). This highlights how social media facilitates indoctrination by creating direct channels for communication, and it's getting easier as social media has accelerated the radicalisation timeline. Studies show that increased exposure to extremist content correlates with faster ideological commitment among jihadist foreign fighters (Anglin, 2023). Platforms like Facebook and Instagram have also been exploited to portray members of extremist groups as heroic figures while marketing their vision of an inevitable victory (Farwell, 2014). These narratives are emotionally charged and designed to resonate with both sympathisers and potential recruits.

One of the most concerning aspects of digital platforms which is incredibly different to mitigate is how algorithms forcibly advertise extremist content, customising itself to appeal the viewer. An article proposed by Purtri et al. (2024), said that algorithms unintentionally create filter bubbles (Pariser, 2011) that magnify false information and extremist content but also limiting access to alternate perspectives (Purtri et al., 2024). Conclusively, it aligns with the notion that YouTube has been found to disproportionately recommend far-right material through their recommender systems. Algorithmic biases have the tendency to amplify the propagation of incorrect information, especially with media that is sensationalist or that matches up with the algorithm design (Selena & Kenney, 2018), will receive a larger priority than any other information without factual reliability (Shin et al., 2022). This is why there is a major epidemic of underprivileged groups being unfairly treated within the media as once an algorithm disregards upcoming information which is accessible to users, it creates a digital environment that neglects their viewpoints (Karitzat et al., 2021), enforcing hate crime and marginalisation. Analysis also shows that YouTube's 'recommendation' page on a viewer's account amplifies extreme content more often than on platforms like Reddit or even Gab, going as far as to say YouTube is a "radicalisation

pipeline” (Schmitt et al., 2018), a study conducted by Whittaker et al. (2021) found users who involve themselves in far-right content are highly exposed to this extremist content, this ultimately reinforces echo chambers (Whittaker, 2021).

3.4 Case Studies: Platform-Specific Exploitation

Particular cases that have shown platform-based exploitation have detected ISIS on platforms like Telegram who create algorithmically monitored chatrooms for recruitment and propaganda to thrive (Valentini et al., 2020). The entire aim of these manufactured chatrooms is to ensure radicalisation is always a possibility and stays constant, even after the Paris attacks in 2015, Twitter’s algorithm indirectly amplified anti-Muslim content by adding these to viewers ‘suggested watches’, further polarising public discourse and promoting retaliatory extremism (Baugut & Neumann, 2019).

Far-right movements on YouTube have taken to broadening their horizons amongst gamers, embedding extremist narratives into seemingly innocent gaming videos. By targeting an audience so affiliated with a younger census, radicalisation succession rates rise as they’re typically more influential and desensitised to extremist content using games like Roblox, Division 2 and Minecraft to indoctrinate the youth, something that the gaming industry have tried to interject and that increasingly angers extremists who refuse to relent (GPAHE, 2024). Closed online communities like Gab and Reddit have become the perfect environments for involuntary celibate men to encounter one another and create misogynistic radicalisation climates, more commonly known as, ‘incels’ (Tietjen & Tirkkonen, 2023). A network of misogynistic groups which are sub culturally known as the “masosphere”, including participation of incels, use the same demeaning language towards women which collectively creates the in-group, victimisation mentality. One study which analysed posts from subreddits over a seven-year period showed an increase in both the frequency and intensity of misogynistic language which highlights how platforms can amplify harmful ideologies (Ellis, 2019).

It is evident how powerful media is at presenting extremist groups and how people are enticed into these groups and these extremists, through social media, praise themselves as spokespeople who partake in grassroots movements (Bergan, 2016) rather than fringe threats (Edgerly & Vraga, 2020) which defines them as being relatable rather than dangerous. These can make them seem more appealing especially to people who feel marginalised or vulnerable in society. This is why government and tech-platforms trying to intervene with leaders who speak on behalf on the groups, find it difficult to make progress without violating free speech. However, in 2024 the UK extremism policy was changed with an updated definition that raised concerns over the actual freedom of speech (Castle, 2024). An

incident which occurred at the University of Sussex saw a professor left jobless after being accused of transphobia in 2021, this intervention shows positive futures for prevention in extremism but doesn't consider extremism groups or Lone Wolf's (Ganor, 2021) who spread hate speech on social media in anonymity (Stanley, 2025). Understanding how media and algorithms shape both radicalisation and public perception is key to responding effectively, especially taking into consideration that extremism policies cannot generalise to all cases of potential exploitation cases.

3.5 Alternative Media and Echo Chambers:

Alternative media and echo chambers (Arguedas et al., 2022) have also become poignant tools in shaping perceptions of extremist groups which often promote unwavering narratives, promoting radicalisation. Some online platforms, commonly known as alternative (Jones et al., 2024) or fringe media (Winkel, 2023), are used as extremist belief dispersers which they label as revealing "truths" that mainstream media try to hide- this appeals to people who already hold a grudge against traditional media and institutions. For instance, platforms like Gab and Parler, which was removed from most app stores online (Culliford, 2021), have less restrictive rules on what content is allowed, making it easier for users to find and share extreme views (Chen et al., 2023). Most media from these platforms either stretch conspiracy theories or strongly biased stories so it looks professionally engaging through videos, podcasts and blogs (Neo et al., 2016). Typically, these groups will use current events to make their messages seem relevant, during the 2020 U.S. elections, alternative media widely promoted the false "Stop the Steal" theory which helped spread extremist beliefs (Influence Watch, 2020). Resultantly, blending misinformation with anti-establishment expression-initiated support for extremist causes (Brzuszkiewicz, 2020).

Online spaces like forums, blogs and certain social media platforms usually become echo chambers, this is where people hear ideas that they already agree with, ideas that they're more susceptible to hearing which only strengthens their beliefs over time (Cinelli et al., 2021). According to social identity theory (SLT), such environments provoke individuals to foster in-group identities that heighten the hostility towards the out-group (Strindberg, 2020). These spaces create a sense of belonging and shared identity, often users will refer to specific language like 'redpilling' which refers back to the niche term 'Red pill' or 'Blue pill' from the 1999 science fiction film, the Matrix. More recently, the term has coined the meaning for someone who has come into a recent reality they were previously concealed from, examples of being red-pilled include: the MAGA movement, vaccine extremism, homophobia, misogyny, incel behaviour and racism (Meirram Webster, 2025). This dynamic is prevalent on the far-right platform Telegram where users congregate together to signify their similar beliefs (Mølmen &

Ravndal, 2021), these communities synthesise a climate for radicalisation. Alternative media doesn't just affect individuals, it changes how society views extremist groups overall, repetition creates normalisation, and constant exposure to terms like "globalist elite" and "great replacement" on alternative, fringe podcasts have been shown to increase acceptance of anti-Semitic or xenophobic behaviour amongst avid listeners (Chen et al., 2023). Alternative media creates a cyclical movement, where people become more extreme in their beliefs, and society becomes more desensitised to the point of accepting those ideas. Mainstream platforms begin by removing/banning extreme content which moves these users onto smaller, fringe platforms and as a result strengthens the ideologies within these echo chambers, making deradicalisation difficult as they become resistant to external critique (Atari et al., 2023).

To effectively stop radicalisation, its important to understand how these alternatives, fringe media spaces work. While big platforms try to control extremist content through moderation, this doesn't apply to smaller sites which are more spread out and way less predictable. Moving onwards from simply removing dangerous content, policy efforts should start by breaking the algorithms which push users towards extreme communities (Frischlich, 2023). At the same time, more initiative needs to go into counter-messages that will definitely connect with people in these echo chambers, without pushing them further away (RAND, 2013).

To conclude, after refining different types of media from traditional news outlets to social media/ fringe platforms, this chapter has shown how different types of media play a major role in shaping public perception of extremist groups, even encouraging radicalisation. Traditional media often uses dramatic and sensationalist language, which draws more attention to certain extremist groups, especially of the Islamic community, while downplaying or normalising others like far-right groups. This unfair reporting can lead to irrational stereotypes, fear, and increased divides in society. Social media has changed how extremist messages are spread, making it easier and faster for these groups to reach people. Groups like ISIS have used platforms like Twitter, YouTube, and Telegram have been used to recruit, radicalise, and spread propaganda. Algorithms also play a key role by showing users more of the same extreme content, which creates the "echo chambers", creating communities of people who feed into each other radical views.

Chapter 4: Media Representation of Extremist Groups

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss how media tends to misrepresent or generalise information about specific groups, looking into specifically how Muslims are associated with terrorism, or painting left-wing groups as anarchists. Equally as relevant to the question at hand, how these portrayals influence public opinion and heighten societal fears. Furthermore, this chapter aims to examine studies which compare how the same group or event is framed differently by different media outlets, and how this affects public opinion. Finally, the issues concerning gender, race and ideology within media representation are discussed in relation to harmful stereotypes, particularly around Muslim communities. Literature which analyses certain language towards stigmatised depictions of terrorists will be explored as well as the promises towards women of becoming jihadi brides and how this effectively works as a recruitment scheme for radicalisers.

4.2 Stigmatisation and Misrepresentation

Media often oversimplifies or changes the perception of certain groups which creates harmful stereotypes that shape public opinions and resultantly amplify societal fears. For instance, Muslims are commonly linked to terrorism in Western media, terms like “Islamist extremists” in news headlines, resonates negative views. Ultimately, this makes people misconceive given media coverage and begin associating Islam with violence, leading to more Islamophobia and increasing discrimination against Muslim communities (Smith, 2020). Similarly, left-wing groups are often described as violent or anarchist (ProtectUK, 2022), while far-right extremism may receive less critical judgement, based on the media outlet’s political views (Brown, 2024). These portrayals not only distort public understanding but also feed into societal tensions and mistrust, sometimes resurrecting old tensions from injustice from the past. The medias tendency to sensationalise terrorism-related news for higher viewership exacerbates these issues, particular research by White, (2020) highlights how fear-driven content is prioritised over balanced reporting which ultimately contributes to a cycle of prejudice and alienation (Feick, 2020). Moreover, De Coster & Veilleux, (2024) present empirical analysis that Muslim-perpetrated attacks receive more negative, sustained coverage in the media than non-Muslim attacks which reiterates societal mistrust. This stigmatisation impacts not only the targeted communities but also public discourse on extremism, making it harder to address underlying socio-political complexities.

4.3 Terrorist vs. Freedom Fighter

the framing of extremist groups varies significantly across media outlets, reflecting ideological biases that shape public perception. Studies reveal how identical acts are labelled “terrorism” or “resistance” depending on political circumstances begin with far-right outlets like Golden Dawn frame Islamist attacks as civilisational threats, whilst left-wing platforms blame oppression as the root causes (Kyriakou, 2017). This selective terminology between “attacker” vs. “terrorist”, alters moral judgements, as De Coster et al. (2024) found computational analysis showed Muslim-perpetrated attacks receive more negative language as well as prolonged coverage than non-Muslim incidents. Western media frequently put culpability on the Muslim community, as seen in post- 9/11 coverage where perpetrators were linked to Al-Qaeda based solely on names before investigations concluded (Rahman & Salma, 2024). This kind of reporting doesn’t just describe events; it shapes stories to fit certain political ideas and mainstream media often use official government terms that support existing power structures, while some alternative outlets use terms like “freedom fighter” to support their own views (Baele & Sterck, 2017). The more these practices reoccur, eventually increases systematic biases (Coster et al., 2024a), with white extremists often framed as “lone actors” while Muslim attackers face immediate “terrorist” branding (De Coster et al. 2024; Rahman & Salma, 2024). This exacerbates polarisation and enables policies to target specific communities.

4.4 Gender, Race, and Ideology in Media Representation

Media representations of extremist groups are deeply shaped by intersecting factors of gender, race and ideology. Groups like ISIS strategically weaponise gender norms in recruitment, targeting women with promises of empowerment as jihadi brides while framing men as predators of religious identity. This tactic is amplified through platforms like Instagram, where extremist content reinforces traditional roles and attacks non-binary identities (Scheuble & Oezmen, 2022; Nolas, 2024). These narratives exploit societal pressures, such as family ties or experiences of marginalisation, to radicalise vulnerable individuals (Darden, 2019; Shafieiou & Haq, 2023). Racial and religious biases further manipulate coverage as Islamist groups receive disproportionate attention compared to far-right extremist, creating stereotypes of Islam as particularly violent (van Stekelenburg, 2017). As previously mentioned in 4.2 within this context chapter, white attackers and non-white attackers are labelled differently throughout media, this only reinforces the double standard rooted in identity salience (Morris, 2013) and framing theory (Smith et al., 2016; Jarvis & Lister, 2017). These portrayals tend to legitimise extremist ideologies by alienating communities and making Muslim populations the perpetual suspects, the counterterrorism Prevent scheme (Counter Terrorism Policing, 2024) in the UK is targeted at Muslim communities which normalises the othering dynamic and ultimately dehumanises an entire

community of people (Wilner & Dubouloz, 2010; Horgan, 2008). To counteract this cycle, media must start to address systematic drivers (Allan et al., 2015) like social injustice and discrimination (Shafieiou & Haq, 2023), while finding reporting that rejects sensationalism and challenges gendered or radicalised stereotypes rooted in extremist propaganda (Mols, 2024; Darden, 2019).

In conclusion, chapter 4 has explored the diverse and often problematic ways in which extremist groups are represented in the media and reveals how coverage is heavily manipulated and influenced by underlying biases related to race, gender and ideology. Media portrayals frequently stigmatise Muslim communities by associating Islam with terrorism, while downplaying far-right extremism, demonstrating a double standard that fuels discrimination and societal divides. The framing of events and individuals, whether as “terrorists” or “freedom fighters”, further highlights the ideological biases of different media outlets and their influence on public perception. Additionally, the strategic use of gendered narratives by extremist groups, and the media’s amplification of these tropes, shows how identity can be weaponised to both recruit and alienate. Together, these patterns of misrepresentation reinforce harmful stereotypes, escalate fear, and changed the understandings of extremism.

Chapter 5: Radicalisation Pathways and Media Influence

5.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss how media serves as a recruitment tool, specifically online, amongst vulnerable individuals who seek for identity, community or a purpose, looking at certain literature which discusses media's role in influencing young people's susceptibility to extremist ideology. The public perception and polarisation created by media narratives can drive individuals towards radical groups by reinforcing ideological divides. Discussions of cases studies including the U.S. 2020 election and the Manchester Areas bomber in 2017 and the relevance these have on individuals that have been radicalised after prolonged exposure to particular media content. Finally, investigating the potential of media to counteract radicalisation by promoting positive narratives, deconstructing extremist ideologies, and offering alternative narratives.

5.2 Recruitment via Media

Media, specifically online, has become a primary tool for identifying and grooming individuals susceptible to extremist ideologies. Radicalisers on social media platforms exploit algorithms and forums to target those experiencing isolation, identity crises, or socio-political alienation (Franc & Pavlovic, 2021). For instance, Daesh's (Welby, 2020) 2014 recruitment campaign used Twitter to spread propaganda tailored to these young women who offered them promises of spiritual fulfilment and sisterhood whilst demonising Western societies (Saltman & Smith, 2015). A key method used is algorithmic amplification, as mentioned in section 3.4 of the themed chapters, is where extremist content tends to thrive in echo chambers that normalise these radical views (O'Callaghan et al., 2014; Huszar et al., 2021). Researchers by Whittaker (2022); Kenyon (2022); Marwick et al. (2022) all found similar results from online radical profiles that are learning new grooming tactics and purposefully transition from public platforms like YouTube or gaming chatrooms into private encrypted chats on alternative media sites such as Telegram where they continue recruitment efforts. Radicalisers have been known to exploit personal issues, such as personal experiences of discrimination and furthermore convincing users that extremism is the solution to rectify these injustices (Vidino & Hughes, 2015). Studies by Yang et al. (2017) highlight that young adults ages 18-24, who spend significant amounts of time online are particularly vulnerable due to developmental struggles with self-identity and belonging,

this is parallel to the incel movement that's recently arose on alternative media platforms, discussed earlier within these contextual chapters (3.3) (Yang et al., 2017).

5.3 Polarisation and Identity Formation

Polarisation created within the media reinforces these ideological factions which push individuals towards radical groups that offer a sense of belonging and community. Empirical results provided from Marwich & Lewis (2017) literature review's show how far-right radicalisation thrives on platforms like Bag and Parler, which welcome conspiracy theories and reinforce in-group/out-group mentalities. Quite similarly, Islamist radicalisation has been linked to prolonged exposure to Islamic State (IS) propaganda, which is accessed through encrypted channels to keep privacy, a well-known example is the case of the Manchester Arena bomber in 2017 (Jones & Hirst, 2023), where prolonged exposure to such strong content strengthens ingroup-outgroup mentalities by creating what's known as reactionary hate (Huszar et al. 2021; Treistman, 2021; KhosraviNik & Esposito, 2018). This is further reinforced through selective news consumption crafted by algorithms which prioritise sensationalistic content (Bakshy et al., 2015) and overall normalisation of extremist content through the process of desensitisation.

5.4 The Role of Media in Counter-Radicalisation

However, whilst the media can fuel radicalisation, there are many ways in which it can mitigate itself through counter-radicalisation programmes. Deradicalisation initiatives like the EU's Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN) use platforms like YouTube and TikTok to challenge extremist propaganda, however, their prevention methods often lag behind the widespread distribution of extremist claims (Start Insight, 2024; European Commission, 2020). Similarly, mentorship schemes described by intervention providers such as Raithelhuber (2023) emphasise rebuilding trust in mainstream communities by offering alternative narratives associated in inclusivity and social community restoration. Conversely, barriers like Islamophobic media bias hinder these efforts where negative portrayals of Muslims within media coverage link them to conflicts in Iraq, Syria and Pakistan. This perpetrates stigmatisation while marginalising spokesperson voices (Ahmed & Matthes, 2016), this is also a cyclical issue as most legitimate community spokespersons are labelled as "terrorism sympathisers" (BBC Trending, 2015) which stifles efforts towards counter-radicalisation, illegitimising their supportive dialogue (Abbas & Awan, 2015). Additionally, as extremist content usually migrates toward alternative, less-regulated spaces such as Telegram or gaming livestreams, moderation effort thus made by YouTube and TikTok depletes moderation efforts (Weimann & Brosius, 2021), further complicating intervention strategies.

Media representations directly influence both radicalisation opportunities and public perceptions of minority groups. Stereotypes of the Muslim community in crime-related backgrounds created stigmatisation and drive some individuals toward extremist networks that promise empowerment (Baugut & Neumann, 2019a). On the other hand, by highlighting diverse voices from marginalised groups, this will help to break the cyclical motion of division within communities. To reduce radicalisation, mitigation programmes like improved media literacy education (Livingstone & Helsper, 2007), platform accountability measures, and justice seen for the marginalised groups effected (Bickert & Fishman, 2017).

This chapter has evaluated the complex relationship between media and radicalisation, highlighting how online platforms can act as recruitment tools for extremist groups. Vulnerable adults, in this instance younger people, are often drawn in through targeted messaging and grooming that exploits personal vulnerabilities and identity struggles. The use of algorithms and echo chambers reinforce the polarisation which leads to an in-group and out-group mentality that push individuals further toward extremist beliefs. Case studies such as the Manchester Arena Bomber and post-2020 U.S. election radicalisation reveal how prolonged exposure to biased or extremist content can shape behaviours and beliefs. Despite it feeding into radicalisation, the media also holds potential to mitigate into counter-radicalisation. mentorship programmes and community-led interventions offer alternative paths, though they are hindered by biased media portrayals and the dispersion of radical content on alternative platforms.

Chapter 6: Public Perception of Extremist Groups

6.1 Introduction

This chapter will discuss the issues concerning the perception of extremist groups, generated by the media, disperses into sub-issues including the creation of “moral panic” and the distortion of facts about these groups. Also, analysis of how public perceptions are manipulated to create fear or demonise certain groups by diving into the War on Terror narrative. Certain studies have been reviewed in relation to how medias portrayal of radicalised groups and how they it can deepen fear and prejudice, contributing to societal divisions and hence the discussion of rising Islamophobia post 9/11. Finally, examining how media representations affect government policies toward extremist groups and how public opinion is shaped by these portrayals.

6.2 Shaping Public Opinion

So far, literature concerning the importance of media has been reviewed, compared and reflected on, and what can be strongly concluded is the pivotal role platforms have in shaping public perceptions of extremist groups, often serving as both a mediator and manipulator of opinion. Through this coverage also, the media can create fear and a sense of “moral panic”, a term coined by Cohen (1972) which involves the process of public anxiety in response to a certain individuals or group being portrayed as threats to societal values and interests. (Cohen, 1972). One significant issue that has occurred is the War on Terror (Grinyer, 2021) which former President George Bush declared post 9/11 attacks, this has been instrumental in demonising specific groups particularly Muslims and Arabs. Stereotypes have since derived from the characters who were responsible for the attacks, depicting these communities as inherently violent or threatening.

6.3 Fear and Stereotyping

Media portrayals of radicalised groups have been shown to deepen societal fear and prejudice, in particular, the aftermath of the 9/11 attacks saw a huge spike in Islamophobia, driven largely by media representations that resulted with terrorism within Islam (Trinh, 2020). Research highlights how these depictions coincide with societal divisions which reinforces stereotypes such as “all terrorists are Muslim” and “White people are never terrorists” while simultaneously excluding white extremists from similar associations (Corbin, 2017). This selective framing creates subconscious biases which alludes

into an 'othering' towards Muslims being seen as a constant threat to society (Whidden, 2021). The idea of moral panic further illustrates how media coverage can lead to complete hysteria by repeatedly broadcasting images and stories that emphasise violence or danger in association with certain groups. Typically, these groups are already victims of marginalisation, and the media fosters a "society of fear" (Ben-Yehuda, 2020) where public concern rapidly disseminates from the lack of faith they had to begin with, this fear often turns into discriminatory behaviours against minority communities, deepening societal fractions.

6.4 Media's Impact on Policy

The medias representation of extremist groups doesn't just affect how people think, it also shapes government policies and when news stories are sensational or focus on fear, governments often respond by making stricter laws, such as increasing surveillance or passing tough counter-terrorism measures (White, 2020). The Patriot Act (Duignan, 2018) in the U.S. is one example of how public fear can lead to policy changes aimed at combating terrorism, similarly, in China, tactics have been adopted under the narrative of addressing "three evils" (Li, 2019) which include terrorism, separatism, and religious extremism. This resulted in widespread prejudice against Muslim communities, with larger reach as governments alarm this through the media which reinforces stereotypes and justify state actions (Vijayendra & Chandrappa, 2019).

This chapter has explored the critical role media plays towards shaping public perception of extremist groups, highlighting how narratives driven by sensationalism and selective representation contribute to moral panics, fear within society and extensive prejudice. Through the analysis of post-9/11 media coverage, particularly the War on Terror narrative, it becomes evident that certain communities, most notably Muslims and Arabs, have been disproportionately targeted and demonised, fostering deep-rooted stereotypes and increasing Islamophobia. These negative depictions have made people more afraid and more likely to believe harmful generalisations, like assuming all terrorists are Muslim. This fear can also lead to governments making stricter laws, such as more surveillance which often targets marginalised groups.

Chapter 7: Conclusion

7.1 Introduction

Through a synthesis of theoretical frameworks, empirical research and real case study examples, it is clear to notice that media representation is not a small factor in reflecting social realities but more of a dominant underlying issue shaping both the process of radicalisation and the wider societal understandings of extremist groups.

7.2 Summary of Key Findings

The analysis began by understanding the issue of radicalisation within contemporary security discourse, more specifically in the context of the UK's counter-terrorism strategies. The literature review demonstrated that media, especially in the online age, has become central to both the propagation of extremist ideologies and the shaping of public perceptions about groups associated with radicalism. Social media platforms, with their algorithmic manipulation and the potential they have to going viral, have amplified these effects, making the question of media influence more urgent than ever. This dissertation's theoretical framework was situated in Media Framing and Cultivation Theory. Media Framing Theory, introduced by scholars such as Goffman and Entman, provided a robust framework for understanding how the presentation of news, through choices of language, emphasis and context, can subtly but powerfully influence public attitudes. The analysis of British media coverage post-9/11, for example, depicted how frames such as "Inevitability and Preparedness" and "Belonging and Responsibility" fuel to the stigmatisation of Muslim communities, reinforcing stereotypes and creating societal mistrust. Cultivation Theory, suggested by Gerbner, further showed how long-term effects of sustained media exposure can alter our perceptions of the world. The concepts of "Mean World Syndrome", mainstreaming, and resonance explained how repeated exposure to certain media stories, particularly those containing violence and extremism, can lead individuals to perceive as more common or threatening than they actually are. The theory's application to the portrayal of crime and ethnicity in the media revealed how these representations can cultivate distorted social realities, which in turn may facilitate the normalisation of extremist ideologies among susceptible individuals.

7.3 Implications for Radicalisation and Public Perception

This research emphasises that media representation plays a dual role in the radicalisation process. On one hand, sensationalised and shallow portrayals of extremist groups can serve as "free advertising",

inadvertently legitimising or glamorising such organisations as the audience of potential recruits. However, on the other hand, negative framing and the association of entire communities with extremism can create alienation, resentment and an all-round sense of injustice, which are well-documented risk factors of radicalisation. Moreover, the media's influence is not justifiably to blame in all cases, this dissertation highlighted the importance of individual differences, such as personal experience, education, and social environment in mediating the effects of media exposure. While some individuals may become more critical or sceptical consumers of information, others may internalise media frames more readily, especially if these resonate with their lived experiences or grievances. This understanding challenges reductionist evaluations of media effects and leaves gaps for more sophisticated approaches to both media literature and counter-radicalisation efforts.

7.4 Limitations and Areas for Future Research

So far, a comprehensive overview of the role of media has been provided, in reference to representation of radicalisation and public perception, however, limitations must be acknowledged. The analysis was primarily qualitative and focused on UK-based case studies, which may limit the generalisability of the findings to other normal or cultural contexts. Additionally, the rapidly evolving technology of social media platforms presents ongoing challenges for researchers, as new forms of content, algorithmic generation, and user interaction continue to reshape the media landscape. Future research should consider comparative studies across different countries and media systems, as well as longitudinal analysis that tracks changes in public perception and radicalisation over time. A concerning part of representation with other factors such as political rhetoric, educational efforts and community engagement also warrants further investigation as these governing powers should be mitigating against misrepresentation with every will they have.

7.5 Policy and Practical Recommendations

The findings of this literature review-based dissertation have important implications for policymakers, media researchers and educators. First, there is a pressing need for more responsible media coverage of extremism and radicalisation, as well as journalists and editors being more careful about what stories they're curating. Framing choices also need to be carefully considered and the potential consequences for stigmatised communities that they create. Second, media literacy initiatives should be expanded to educate the public with the critical skills necessary to recognise and resist manipulative frames. Third, counter-radicalisation strategies must move beyond surveillance and policing to address the underlying social and psychological instigators of radicalisation, including the role of media in shaping identity and belonging.

7.6 Conclusion

In conclusion, media representation is a powerful force in the construction, deconstruction and distortion of social realities, shaping public opinion, and the pathways to radicalisation. By critically engaging with the ways in which media frames and cultivates perceptions of extremist groups, this dissertation has highlighted both the risks and opportunities prevalent in contemporary media environments, as we all recognised traditional media issues. Ultimately, by taking on a more informed, critical and empathetic approach to media consumption is essential, not only for countering radicalisation but most importantly to begin building a more inclusive, trusting and resilient society.

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